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Ukrainian refugee children in Czech early childhood settings: why some families are more successful than others when integrating into a new environment

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ABSTRACT

This study applies the Community Cultural Wealth (CCW) framework to examine the experience of Ukrainian refugee families with young children adapting to early childhood education and care in the Czech Republic after 2022. Based on 15 semi-structured interviews with Ukrainian mothers, it highlights the types of community cultural wealth used to navigate Czech society, access early childhood education and adapt to Czech ECEC settings. The results show that social and familial capitals played a positive role upon arrival. Many families also demonstrated considerable resistant and navigational capital, reacting quickly and flexibly to participate in Czech society. Although the use of these capitals was restricted during the uncertain integration phase, they were fully utilised when overcoming challenges, especially with complex admission processes for limited ECEC places. Utilisation of the family's linguistic capital was key to integrating children, but resistant capital was most useful in compensating for socio-cultural and linguistic barriers.

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Introduction

More than 680,000 Ukrainian war refugees have entered the Czech Republic since Russia invaded Ukraine. While Poland received the highest total number of Ukrainian refugees, the Czech Republic received the most in terms of refugees per 100,000 inhabitants (Eurostat 2024). This influx has strained public services, including education and care systems. Most Ukrainians granted temporary protection (approximately 350,000) are mostly women with children who remain in the Czech Republic. In line with the EU position, Ukrainian refugees received temporary protection status and generous rights, including access to the labour market, education, and health care. Although mainly mothers with children (28% under 18), these refugees quickly started participating in the labour market (PAQ Research 2023).

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Most families with young children sought early childhood education and care (ECEC) after arriving. Around 34% of refugee children attended *pre-schools* and 4% *children's groups* in June 2022, increasing to 69% and 5% respectively by June 2023 (Šafářová et al. 2023). In June 2023, there were 13,532 Ukrainian children aged 4–6 in the Czech Republic (MI CR 2023). However, data on ECEC attendance is indicative due to population fluctuation and different data sources. Another survey (MEYS 2023) found that the ECEC participation rate among Ukrainian children was significantly lower, at 48%. Both surveys show increased attendance in the compulsory last year of pre-primary education, indicating reduced availability of ECEC services in non-compulsory years. Limited access to ECEC provision was exacerbated by the lack of agencies to help families find affordable childcare solutions. Amid a general shortage of ECEC capacity in the Czech Republic (CSI 2023), refugee families' access to ECEC depended on their place of residence and available community cultural wealth. Limited access poses a major barrier to integration, employment (Jelínková, Ochrana, and Plaček 2023), and the goal of quality ECEC for all (UN 2015).

This study explores the experiences of Ukrainian refugees with the ECEC system in the Czech Republic from the perspective of refugee mothers. The research questions explore which forms of Community Cultural Wealth (CCW) mothers mobilised to navigate the ECEC system, secure access to provision, and support their children's adjustment. The article contributes to the field in three keyways: (1) by applying the CCW framework in a post-socialist Central European context; (2) by offering empirical insights into forced migration and institutional integration in early childhood education; and (3) by foregrounding the voices and strategies of refugee mothers navigating complex educational systems. The findings illustrate how different forms of CCW were mobilised to access ECEC and support children's integration, while also revealing structural barriers and institutional shortcomings that frequently constrained these efforts.

The Czech ECEC system and its response to Ukrainian refugees

European countries have taken diverse approaches to support the integration of Ukrainian children into ECEC settings (OECD 2023). In the Czech Republic, participation in pre-primary education is mandatory for all children, including Ukrainian refugees, starting at age 5, despite significant capacity gaps in the ECEC system.

The Czech ECEC system is organised as a split system (Loudová Stralczynská 2024). Pre-primary education is provided in (1) pre-schools (ages 2–6) and (2) preparatory classes (ages 5–7) in primary schools. Children from age 3 have a legal entitlement to a pre-school place, and pre-primary education is compulsory for children aged 5 by 31 August, including migrants staying over 90 days. Due to insufficient capacity, the system is supplemented by costly facilities like (3) children's groups (ages 6 months to compulsory schooling) and (4) childcare facilities for children under 3, which are not part of the education system and are primarily socialising and caring in nature. This ECEC structure has been criticised for hindering effective coordination of high-quality provision and affordable, accessible care (OECD 2019, 2020; Lynch, Basarabová, and Loudová Stralczynská 2023).

Commitment to integrate children into the education system

The Czech education and care system aimed to help newly arrived children adapt to Czech society (CSI 2023), and the Lex Ukraine legislation was introduced for those granted temporary protection. Temporary special children's groups and adaptation groups were established but faced systemic barriers. These included uneven regional provision, time-limited eligibility (usually 90 days), lack of stable funding, and reliance on NGOs for staffing and facilities. In many cases, adaptation groups lacked qualified ECEC staff, interpreters, or structured language support. By 2022, many children from adaptation groups were included in regular pre-schools (CSI 2023; Šafářová et al. 2023).

Despite requirements for pre-schools to enrol every applicant from age three in the school district, many Ukrainian child refugees remained outside the education system (31% in June 2023, Šafářová et al. 2023). Reasons included rejection due to lack of places (59%), lack of knowledge of the enrolment process (15%), child's lack of Czech knowledge (7%), and intention to return to Ukraine (5%) (PAQ Research 2023). Early and quality educational support is crucial for further education (Borgna and Contini 2014; Weikart 2000). Limited ECEC capacity also decreases parental labour market participation, which doesn't support children's wider social development. Access to quality ECEC services provides stimuli for comprehensive development, enabling children to experience a safe community and develop necessary competencies (Atteberry, Bassok, and Wong 2019; Stevens, Siraj, and Kong 2023). Systemic barriers in Czech ECEC hinder integration, with no coordination between facilities and little help for families to find solutions. Families navigate the local ECEC offer with help from social networks and NGOs (Jelínková, Plaček, and Ochrana 2024).

Comparison with Ukraine

ECEC systems in the Czech Republic and Ukraine are similar (Putcha et al. 2018), but Ukrainian children participate more in institutional care for infants, while in the Czech Republic, long parental leave reduces institutional care for children under 3 (Oberhuemer and Schreyer 2024). Pedagogical approaches differ, with Ukraine favouring teacher-led pedagogy and the Czech system favouring more child-centred pedagogy. The Czech system aims to respect each child's needs, develop their potential, and create conditions for participation and active learning (Opravilová 2016).

Theoretical framework

The Community Cultural Wealth (CCW) framework (Yosso 2005) is applied in this study to capture how Ukrainian parents navigated the ECEC system and how their children adapted to ECEC settings (mainly pre-schools). This framework is particularly useful because it shifts attention from viewing refugee families through a deficit lens to recognising the assets and strategies they mobilise in integration. Traditional interpretations of Bourdieusian cultural capital theory (Bourdieu and Passeron 1977) emphasise dominant, middleclass forms of cultural knowledge and dispositions as the basis for educational success, thereby marginalising families who lack these forms. Yosso (2005) challenges this perspective by introducing CCW, which identifies a range of capitals—including aspirational, familial, social, linguistic, navigational, and resistant—that refugee families draw upon to overcome barriers and

participate in education, thereby recognising nondominant forms of knowledge and experience as valuable resources in educational contexts. Importantly, Yosso grounds CCW in Critical Race Theory (CRT), arguing that cultural capital must be understood in relation to power, race, and inequality. By integrating CRT with CCW, she highlights how systemic inequities shape which forms of knowledge and resources are recognised or devalued and underscores that communities of colour and migrant families actively generate and transmit nondominant forms of knowledge that foster adaptation and resilience. This integration makes CCW a particularly powerful framework for analysing how minoritized populations navigate educational institutions while simultaneously confronting structural barriers to full inclusion. In what follows, each of the six forms of CCW is briefly outlined to illustrate their relevance for understanding the experiences of Ukrainian refugee families in Czech ECEC settings.

Aspirational capital refers to the ability to maintain hopes and dreams for the future, even in the face of real and perceived barriers. This resiliency is evidenced in those who allow themselves and their children to dream of possibilities beyond their present circumstances, often without the objective means to achieve those goals. *Linguistic* capital includes skills attained through communication in more than one language or style. *Familial* capital refers to cultural knowledge nurtured among kin, carrying a sense of community history and cultural intuition. *Social* capital involves networks of people and resources providing support to navigate society's institutions. *Navigational* capital refers to skills for manoeuvring through social institutions, acknowledging individual agency within constraints and connecting to social networks. *Resistant* capital involves knowledge and skills fostered through oppositional behaviour challenging inequality (Yosso 2005, 77–81).

Although originally developed to study communities of colour in the U.S., CCW has since been applied to diverse educational contexts, including work on refugee children and parental engagement (e.g. Anderson et al. 2023; Boit et al. 2023; Oddy et al. 2022). Its application in Central and Eastern Europe, however, remains rare, with a few exceptions (Obrovská and Janků 2021; Omeni 2016). This study contributes to filling this gap by applying CCW to Ukrainian refugee families in Czech ECEC settings.

Research aim and research questions

The research aims to shed light on Ukrainian mothers with young children and their experiences with the Czech ECEC system. Using the CCW framework, we analyse how the six forms of capital manifest in these mothers and shape their ability to navigate a new environment, secure access to ECEC provision, and support their children's integration. Therefore, the research questions are as follows:

RQ1: Which forms of CCW did participants use to orient themselves in the new environment after arriving in the Czech Republic?

RQ2: Which forms of CCW did Ukrainian refugees use when searching for ECEC provision in the Czech Republic?

RQ3: Which forms of CCW were used when integrating the child into a Czech ECEC setting?

Data and methods

Given the unexplored nature of the topic, we adopted a qualitative exploratory multi-case study (Flick 2009). Semi-structured interviews with 15 Ukrainian mothers in various regions of the Czech Republic. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 15 Ukrainian mothers across regions of the Czech Republic, selected based on refugee distribution and municipal size (CVVM 2024), to capture institutional differences and local specificities. While thematic saturation was approached within our sample, we do not claim full saturation; the findings should therefore be considered exploratory. Respondents ($n = 15$) were chosen according to the child's age (3–6 years) and experience with Czech ECEC: adaptation group ($n = 5$), pre-school ($n = 5$), preparatory class ($n = 2$), and both adaptation group and pre-school ($n = 3$). This purposeful sampling reflected the full typology of ECEC options while limiting duplication of experiences. Focusing exclusively on mothers mirrors the gendered refugee population in 2022–2023 but may reinforce assumptions about caregiving roles; fathers and other caregivers were not included, which we acknowledge as a limitation.

Interviews, conducted between March and November 2023, lasted 30–40 minutes and followed a script developed from field knowledge, prior research, literature, and the theoretical framework. They covered background, ECEC experiences, balancing work and childcare, classroom adaptation, communication with institutions, and language roles. A Ukrainian-speaking researcher conducted the interviews to minimise language barriers. The research team combined Czech- and Ukrainian-speaking members with experience in migration and education studies. Ethical approval (no. 83/2023) was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Charles University. Table 1.

Interviews were recorded, transcribed verbatim, anonymised, and translated into Czech using AI, then checked and edited. Data were coded in MAXQDA through open coding, with codes grouped into categories and analysed thematically (Šedová and Švaříček 2013).

Table 1. Respondents' characteristics.

Nº	ECEC settings attended by the child in Czech Republic	Age of the child at the beginning of ECEC attendance	Place of family residence	Arrival to the Czech Republic	Child's previous ECEC participation in Ukraine
1	Adaptation group	4	City	3/2022	YES
2	Adaptation group	6	City	7/2022	YES
3	Adaptation group	3	City	4/2022	YES
4	Adaptation group	3	Town	4/2022	NO
5	Adaptation group	3	Capital city	3/2022	YES
6	Pre-school	3	Village	3/2022	YES
7	Pre-school	6	Town	4/2022	YES
8	Pre-school	3	Capital city	8/2022	YES
9	Pre-school	6	Capital city	3/2022	YES
10	Pre-school	5	City	3/2022	YES
11	Adaptation group and then pre-school	5	Town	3/2022	YES
12	Adaptation group and then pre-school	4	City	3/2022	YES
13	Adaptation group and then pre-school	4	Capital city	4/2022	YES
14	Preparatory class	6	Capital city	6/2022	YES
15	Preparatory class	6	Capital city	8/2022	YES

Table 2. Analytical categories induced in qualitative analysis and their links to RQ1-3.

RQ	Categories	Description of the categories	Signs of capitals
RQ1	Social conditions and contacts	Social relations of the families in their place of residence and in the Czech Republic, which influence their integration into the Czech environment and are reflected in some form in the provision of care for children in the families of the respondents.	Czech and Ukrainian acquaintances, social media information, NGO's support, access to labour market
	Labour market participation	Working conditions of mothers, very often with a direct or indirect relationship to the use of ECEC provision.	Support of friends and family, community support, types of labour market participation
	Language	Individual contexts for learning Czech, specific parental motivations for learning Czech.	Perspective to remain in the Czech Republic, visions of future, proficiency in different languages, communication competencies
RQ2	Searching for an ECEC provision	Individual stories of gaining an ECEC place in the Czech Republic	Language competencies, persistence, personal capacities, access to information, orientation in local context
RQ3	Barriers to enrolment	The different types of barriers encountered by families when looking for an ECEC place for their child.	Personal capacities, access to information, language competencies, social contacts, reflection of child's needs
	Support of child's adaptation	Support measures provided by ECEC settings to facilitate children's adaptation to the Czech environment and their integration into peer groups.	Targeted individual support of the child, parental expectations
	Parent–ECEC setting communication	Strategies used by ECEC settings to communicate with families about care, support, and education, while addressing language and cultural barriers.	Language and communication competencies (and flexibility to use them), personal expectations (ability to modify them)

Categories were compared, clustered (Table 2), and linked to research questions to identify the types of capitals (Yosso 2005) most relevant to the study.

Results

The findings show how Ukrainian parents mobilised different, often interlinked, forms of CCW to navigate the Czech ECEC system and support their children's integration (Yosso 2005). To contextualise these processes, the initial phase examined families' migration trajectories.

Capitals used by Ukrainian families after arrival

The capitals mobilised by respondents varied considerably, shaped by concerns about security and future prospects. Aspirational capital, in particular, was constrained by uncertainty over the length of stay in the Czech Republic. Family separation and questions around residency status further undermined motivation to invest resources in building a life there.

At the moment, we don't plan to stay in the Czech Republic forever. How will that be? We don't deny that we won't go back . . . If the war were to end here, we would definitely go back to Ukraine. We'll decide depending on how long we will stay here. (R3)

Some initially passive respondents modified their approach after a few months, focusing on steps for temporary stability.

We don't even know our plans ... In the beginning I wanted to go home, but now we are getting used to it and we'll learn Czech. In the future, maybe we'll stay, maybe we'll go home ... (R4)

Aspirations for future life sometimes led to helping other Ukrainians, such as finding work as an assistant pedagogical workforce or offering psychological services.

Linguistic capital, enhanced by knowledge of several languages, was crucial for social integration and understanding the ECEC system. Many respondents spoke Russian, English, or Czech, facilitating understanding of the system and societal expectations. There was a positive association between parents' and children's linguistic capital, manifested in better social and communication skills, including non-verbal communication activities and games. Some children refused to use Russian to communicate in ECEC settings.

Respondents' approach to learning Czech reflected their future aspirations and opportunities. Lack of ECEC provision sometimes negatively affected acquiring Czech and attending language courses.

In the beginning I took several courses. And now I don't have the time. (R3)

Familial capital encompasses community history, memory, and supports community well-being. It often played a key role in choosing the Czech Republic as a destination and strengthened mothers in coping with practical and emotional challenges. Respondents highlighted the importance of friendship bonds and the feeling of not being alone, which led to their arrival in the Czech Republic. Familial capital within wider family ties was also a key source of information and assistance in navigating the Czech ECEC system and arranging childcare.

I came with my mother and sisters. Only because of my sister, we could take care of my daughter. (R12)

Having family/community support and securing a place for the children was crucial for entering the labour market. Although most respondents worked regular hours and found jobs upon arrival, many struggled with ECEC facility hours or teacher expectations. Familial capital helped overcome these barriers.

Social capital was essential in choosing the Czech Republic and orienting within Czech society, including the ECEC system. Respondents often approached distant community members identified through networks like relatives, neighbours, or church contacts.

Because many of our compatriots worked here before the war. (R3)

Social capital was enhanced by intensive use of social networks (e.g. Facebook, Telegram), facilitating information searches in various groups. Many support and information groups were created on social media, where compatriots shared experiences about life in the Czech Republic. Other important sources of social capital were supportive contacts in the place of residence, usually Czechs, with whom they had developed relationships.

Our neighbours helped us a lot with finding a school and daycare for our children. (R7)

All respondents had some **navigational** and **resistant** capital, proven by their migration journey, but their ability to cope with barriers varied. Several respondents

adapted to diverse and challenging conditions, finding ways to deal with their situation. For example, one mother arranged for her child to travel to an ECEC setting once a week by bus accompanied only by the teacher, due to long commuting distance and work obligations. In the Czech context, this is highly unusual, as national legislation requires that children be handed over to ECEC settings by an authorised person. Persistent difficulties led to lowered aspirations and acceptance of precarious employment, often restricted to jobs aligned with ECEC hours.

Local community centres and NGOs also helped Ukrainian refugees navigate the complex Czech ECEC system, providing practical information and strategies for overcoming institutional constraints.

Capitals used by Ukrainian families to find an ECEC place

In the search for childcare outside the family, **familial**, **resistant**, and **navigational** capital were most present, enabling families to create strategies to overcome challenges. Nevertheless, all respondents experienced difficulties finding a place in ECEC settings. Families were primarily interested in public pre-schools for affordability, but these were often unavailable due to capacity issues. The search for a public pre-school typically involved months of phone calls and visits to multiple pre-schools. In some cases, mothers received a list of facilities from the municipality but were rejected due to capacity or referred to hard-to-reach pre-schools, leading them to choose private facilities or adaptation groups. Ukrainian families had to make significantly more effort than Czech families, who often secured places by enrolling in two or three pre-schools. Ukrainian families also struggled to find places for children over age 3, legally entitled to pre-school, or those over 5, required to attend compulsory pre-primary education, as they usually missed the enrolment period in May.

We tried to find an ordinary city pre-school in our city, but there were no places, although our daughter was 3 years old then. They said the child was small and there were no places. (R12)

Our daughter went to this day-care (...) for a year. And from next year when the opportunity arises, we will look for a public pre-school. (R12)

Some families used their **social** capital, receiving help from Czech neighbours or friends. Adaptation groups often advertised through social networks focused on helping Ukrainian refugees.

Through integration centre, which helps Ukrainians, we looked for a Czech pre-school, but there was no available place in the city at all. We were late, the groups were full. (R5)

An example of randomly obtaining a place was a mother who responded to a Facebook advert for a pedagogical position in an adaptation group, securing a place for her child.

Some parents consciously used their **aspirational** capital, delaying the search for a pre-school to allow their children to adapt to the new environment. Their decision-making was influenced by considerations of short-term residence in the Czech Republic.

Families and capitals used when integrating children into ECEC settings

Exploiting the family's **linguistic** capital was key to integrating children into Czech ECEC provision. Children and parents demonstrated the ability to use different language registers and communication styles (e.g. electronic communication, social networks, interpreters). Initially, children used alternative communication tools (non-verbal, pictograms, help from another child or assistant). Families adjusted these tools based on ECEC institutions' functioning and their own capacities (e.g. preparing basic Czech phrases found online).

Many parents and children were challenged by the different pedagogical approaches and daily routines in Czech pre-schools, which are more flexible compared to the more structured regimes in Ukraine. This variability was both appreciated and seen as an element of uncertainty. Parents initially found it difficult to adapt but adjusted after a few months. Children found the irregularity challenging at first but quickly appreciated it. The more open pedagogical approach left parents uncertain about the quality of education, but this concern diminished as their children progressed and received individual attention from teachers.

Some parents worked hard to eliminate the language barrier by teaching their children essential Czech phrases:

For starters, I prepared it for him. I prepared a few phrases, a few words, a few essentials as "I don't understand", "I want to drink", or "I need to go to the toilet", to make him feel normal.
(R11)

Other parents learned Czech with their children or arranged for Czech teachers at home, finding language support in Ukrainian adaptation groups insufficient. A summer course at a community centre was also mentioned as a positive measure. Some parents supported their children's language development in Ukrainian, recognizing the need for comprehensive communication competence development.

Parents needed to use their **resistant** capital to compensate for socio-cultural and language barriers in the Czech system. This was most visible when children had adaptation problems, requiring daily information transfer or communication with professionals. Some Czech pre-schools lacked understanding of single-parent situations, repeatedly calling parents to pick up their children due to adaptation issues, even when the parents needed to be at work not to lose their family's financial security.

Regarding the integration of the child into the ECEC setting, we might focus not only on the activities of families, but also on how Ukrainian parents reflected on **children's capitals**. Parents reported that children's specific characteristics and personality often influenced adaptation problems. We might consider to what extent the children were able to use especially their **resilient** and **linguistic capitals** as, according to the parents' statements, all children needed targeted external adult support to be able to successfully adapt in Czech pre-schools, as part of the ECEC system. For example, with some children, the parents attended the facility together on the first day or during the first and second week. In some pre-schools, a teacher's assistant or targeted work by the teacher aimed at emotional support and socialisation of the child in the group effectively helped the child to adapt.

Yes, I felt it very powerfully. On the one hand, the teachers gave my son space to play independently (. . .). They involved him in joint games or drawing, but they didn't push him if he didn't want to. I think if they had insisted, he would have reacted with resistance. On the other hand, they always outlined certain rules for him, or what they were going to do, or where they were going to go, and made sure he understood everything, so he didn't feel left out of the process. (R7)

Only one parent mentioned that the pre-school developed an individual education plan for the child. All respondents reported a positive climate and respectful attitude of teachers, supporting the adaptation process, despite various difficulties.

It was a very difficult period. But we understood that our daughter needs this community. That's why we "rushed" to the pre-school. The teacher there told me that at the beginning, my daughter was taking everything away from the children. But it didn't last long . . . (R6)

The fact that there was a teacher's assistant definitely improved the situation because there were still difficult situations. (R12)

Families experienced both good and difficult adaptation periods. Some children had problems adapting due to socio-cultural and language barriers, leading parents to seek places in adaptation groups. These groups served as 'bridging institutions', strengthening children's ability to cope with change, highlighting the diversity of children's needs and their different abilities to use their competences and capitals in new situations.

Discussion

This study shows how Ukrainian refugee mothers mobilised different forms of CCW to navigate barriers in Czech ECEC and support their children's adaptation. While prior research has emphasised lower participation of refugee children due to structural barriers and the importance of early inclusion (Busch and Leyendecker 2019; Christoph, Elisabeth, and Gisela 2021; Koehler and Schneider 2019; Vigil and Lynn Lopez 2020), this study foregrounds the assets families bring. Applying the CCW framework (Yosso 2005) reveals why some families managed integration more successfully and highlights the need for further research on those excluded from ECEC and on the longterm implications of capital mobilisation in Central Europe.

These findings extend CCW scholarship, which has mainly concentrated on identifying and categorising types of capital, by adding a crucial temporal dimension to the analysis of forced migration. Our findings reveal that expectations about the duration of stay strongly influenced families' readiness to invest in their future in Czechia and, in turn, shaped the activation of capitals. As time horizons shifted, so did strategies of use.

Upon arrival (RQ1), many families demonstrated resistant capital, reacting fast and flexibly. Social and familial capitals were crucial in early childcare arrangements, often reinforced by socio-cultural proximity (Kobzová 2019). Parents' need to join the labour market and support their children's socialisation further stimulated integration (FRA 2023). These findings align with UNICEF research on ECEC's potential to offset trauma and displacement (Vindrola et al. 2023). Yet, as mentioned above, uncertainty about the future reduced parents' motivation to invest in language learning or deeper engagement, thereby limiting the mobilisation of linguistic and navigational capital (Brzozowska 2023; Koehler and Schneider 2019). Many parents, therefore, relied on Ukrainian-speaking

adaptation groups, which eased transition but offered limited educational and linguistic support.

The most prevalent capitals in the search for childcare (RQ2) were familial, resistant, and navigational. Mothers had to make considerable efforts to find adequate ECEC settings (CSI 2023). For children without access to public pre-schools, adaptation groups, discontinued in 2023, had provided a vital bridge to Czech education (PAQ 2023). When searching for childcare, mothers relied heavily on digital resources such as Facebook and Telegram groups to obtain practical advice, typically verified through trusted contacts. Compared to Czech families, they depended far less on official information channels, such as institutional websites or email communication, as well as on longstanding informal networks. This interplay of social and navigational strategies underscores the importance of context-specific reception conditions in shaping capital mobilisation.

While we did not collect formal data on participants' educational levels, national reports suggest that a large proportion of Ukrainian refugees in the Czech Republic are highly educated (CVVM 2024). This likely shaped the kinds of CCW mobilised, particularly linguistic and navigational capital. Importantly, rather than reflecting fear of institutions, navigational capital manifested in distinctive strategies of information-seeking and verification, combining the above-mentioned digital forums with trusted contacts and personal experience. These findings underscore the need to contextualise CCW within specific refugee demographics and reception conditions, which fundamentally shape how capitals are enacted.

Alongside these digital strategies, social capital played a similarly crucial role. Families drew on relatives, friends, Czech acquaintances to secure information and support. This interplay of social and navigational resources was especially visible in the search for childcare places, where several respondents demonstrated considerable resistant capital, persisting with applications despite repeated rejections (cf. Tobin and Kurban 2018).

Linguistic and resistant capitals were essential for children's integration (RQ3). The ability to communicate and exercise resistance helped families overcome educational system differences and adapt to the new environment (Hurley et al. 2011). Parents perceived the language barrier as a major obstacle and often addressed their children's development in this respect (Tobin and Kurban 2018). Respondents reported relatively smooth integration into ECEC settings, mainly pre-schools, often supported by targeted measures such as teaching assistants and Czech language provision, which engaged children's cultural wealth capital (Erdemir 2022). These measures, together with supportive teacher attitudes and overall satisfaction with ECEC, helped alleviate parental concerns about differing pedagogical practices. Parents whose children attended adaptation groups highlighted their value in facilitating the transition to Czech public education. They also appreciated the personal benefits, as attendance enabled them to work or manage family responsibilities.

Despite state support from 2022, systemic shortcomings—capacity shortages, limited pedagogical readiness, and weak institutional preparedness—continued to constrain access (CSI 2023; Stanković, Zorić, and Jovanović 2020). Trauma, fear, and perceived exclusion further undermined mobilisation (Boukhari 2025; Hall and Werner 2022). Individual teacher empathy often compensated for institutional unpreparedness, underscoring gaps between personal commitment and systemic readiness. This contradiction highlights how individual empathy often compensated for systemic gaps.

The predominance of mothers in our sample reflects broader refugee dynamics, where caregiving responsibilities often fall disproportionately on women (Van Ee et al. 2013). These gendered dynamics directly influenced capital mobilisation, as caregiving burdens limited mothers' time, confidence, and opportunities to engage with institutions. Following Yosso's (2005) call to situate CCW within structural conditions, we argue that displacement contexts complicate the activation of capitals. Future research should include fathers and other caregivers to capture these dynamics more fully.

These findings align with the concept that early childhood education has a unique relationship with the family, co-creating a rich environment for the child's education and socialization (Cohen and Anders 2020).

Conclusion and final remarks

This study set out to explain why some Ukrainian refugee mothers were more successful than others in securing places for their children in Czech ECEC. Consistent with previous research (Erdemir 2022; Jarrett and Coba-Rodriguez 2017; Nygård 2022), our findings highlight the decisive role of different forms of capital. Only a few respondents accessed provision with relative ease—usually through a combination of social and linguistic capital and favourable local conditions. For most, however, the process was demanding, requiring the mobilisation of all available resources. These mothers often went far beyond usual practices to secure housing, coordinate schedules, and access services, confirming that parental capitals fundamentally shape children's educational trajectories (Şengönül 2022).

Refugee mothers frequently achieved what Czech families access through institutional or informal support, but under far more constrained conditions. While post-2022 state measures provided broad assistance, long-standing systemic challenges in Czech ECEC—capacity shortages, limited pedagogical flexibility, and lack of intercultural preparedness—continue to impose disproportionate burdens on refugee families.

The findings underscore the need to address these systemic barriers and to strengthen targeted support for equitable access and meaningful integration in early childhood education. They also carry important practical implications. Initial and continuing teacher education should include preparation for working with multilingual children and families, trauma-informed approaches, and culturally sustaining pedagogy. Institutional capacity-building is likewise essential to enable ECEC settings to become more inclusive and responsive to the needs of displaced families. Beyond the empirical insights, this study contributes to CCW by emphasising the temporal, gendered, and structural dimensions of capital mobilisation, showing how forced migration contexts reshape both the potential and the limits of families' cultural wealth.

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References

- Anderson, V., S. Mostolizadeh, J. Oranje, A. Fraser-Smith, and E. Crampton. 2023. “Navigating the Secondary-Tertiary Education Border: Refugee-Background Students in Southern Aotearoa New Zealand.” *Research Papers in Education* 38 (2): 250–275. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2021.1961300>.
- Atteberry, A., D. Bassok, and V. C. Wong. 2019. “The Effects of Full-Day Prekindergarten: Experimental Evidence of Impacts on Children’s School Readiness.” *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis* 41 (4): 537–562. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373719872197>.
- Boit, R. J., A. C. Eastern, S. Bayer, J. C. Birabwa, M. McKoy, and L. L. Hestenes. 2023. “Navigating Educational Success for Their Young Children in the United States: Refugee Families Draw from Their Experiences.” *Early Childhood Education Journal*. June. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-023-01522-7>.
- Borgna, C., and D. Contini. 2014. “Migrant Achievement Penalties in Western Europe: Do Educational Systems Matter?” *European Sociological Review* 30 (5): 670–683. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcu067>.
- Boukhari, S. 2025. “The Relational Refugee Child: Trauma-Informed and Culturally Responsive Approaches to Educational Inclusion.” *Education Sciences* 15 (6): 649. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15060649>.
- Bourdieu, P., and J.-C. Passeron. 1977. *Reproduction in Education, Society and Culture*. 2 ed. Reprinted. Theory, Culture & Society. London: Sage Publ.
- Brzozowska, A. 2023. ““All Is Not Yet Lost Here.” The Role of Aspirations and Capabilities in Migration Projects of Ukrainian Migrants in Poland.” *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 49 (9): 2373–2390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2022.2157804>.
- Busch, J., and B. Leyendecker. 2019. “Socialization and Development of Refugee Children: Chances of Childcare.” In *Children’s Social Worlds in Cultural Context*, edited by T. Tulviste, D. L. Best, and J. L. Gibbons, 187–200. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27033-9_14.
- Christoph, H., L. Elisabeth, and W. Gisela. 2021. “The Role of Socioeconomic, Cultural, and Structural Factors in Daycare Attendance Among Refugee Children.” *Journal for Educational Research Online* 2021 (1): 16–77. April. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:22065>.
- Cohen, F., and Y. Anders. 2020. “Family Involvement in Early Childhood Education and Care and Its Effects on the Social-Emotional and Language Skills of 3-Year-Old Children.” *School Effectiveness and School Improvement* 31 (1): 125–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2019.1646293>.
- CSI. 2023. Průběžná Zpráva o Integraci a Vzdělávání Ukrajinských Děti a Žáků/Interim Report on the Integration and Education of Ukrainian Children and Pupils. Tematická Zpráva/Thematic Report. Praha: Czech School Inspectorate. https://www.csicr.cz/CSICR/media/Prilohy/2022_p%C5%99%C3%ADlohy/Dokumenty/Prubezna-zprava-o-integraci-a-vzdelavani-ukrajinskych-deti-a-zaku.pdf.
- CVVM. 2024. *Ukrajínští uprchlíci v České republice 2024/Ukrainian refugees in the Czech Republic 2024*. Praha: Public Opinion Research Centre.

- Erdemir, E. 2022. "Uncovering Community Cultural Wealth Through an Early Intervention Program: Syrian Refugee Children Speaking." *Early Childhood Education Journal* 50 (2): 259–278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-020-01140-7>.
- Eurostat. 2024. "Migration and Asylum in Europe—2023 Edition". ISBN: 978-92-68-04508-4. Eurostat. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/migration-2023#about-this-publication>.
- Flick, U. 2009. *An Introduction to Qualitative Research*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: Sage Publications.
- FRA. 2023. *Fleeing Ukraine: Displaced People's Experiences in the EU: Ukrainian Survey 2022*. LU: European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2811/855252>.
- Hall, J., and K. Werner. 2022. "Trauma and Trust: How War Exposure Shapes Social and Institutional Trust Among Refugees." *Frontiers in Psychology* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.786838>.
- Hurley, J. J., A. Medici, E. Stewart, and Z. Cohen. 2011. "Supporting Preschoolers and Their Families Who Are Recently Resettled Refugees." *Multicultural Perspectives* 13 (3): 160–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15210960.2011.594400>.
- Jarrett, R. L., and S. Coba-Rodriguez. 2017. "'We Keep the Education Goin' at Home All the Time': Family Literacy in Low-Income African American Families of Preschoolers." *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk (JESPAR)* 22 (2): 57–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10824669.2017.1295861>.
- Jelínková, M., F. Ochrana, and M. Plaček. 2023. "Příchod Ukrajinských Uprchlíků Perspektivou Obcí v Česku/Arrival of Ukrainian Refugees the Perspective of Municipalities in the Czech Republic (Accepted in Print)." *Geografie* 128 (3): 128 (3). <https://doi.org/10.37040/geografie.2023.014>.
- Jelínková, M., M. Plaček, and F. Ochrana. 2024. "Achieving Better Integration of Ukrainian Refugees in the Czech Republic: Making Use of Expertise and Addressing Cultural Differences." *Nonprofit Policy Forum* <https://doi.org/10.1515/npf-2023-0059>.
- Kobzová, P. 2019. "The Czech Republic Through the Eyes of Ukrainians." *Edukacja Międzykulturowa* 10 (1): 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.15804/em.2019.01.07>.
- Koehler, C., and J. Schneider. 2019. "Young Refugees in Education: The Particular Challenges of School Systems in Europe." *Comparative Migration Studies* 7 (1): 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-019-0129-3>.
- Loudová Stralczynská, B. 2024. "Czech Republic—Key Contextual Data." In *Early Childhood Workforce Profiles in 30 Countries with Key Contextual Data*, edited by I. Schreyer, 359–381. München: Staatsinstitut für Frühpädagogik. <https://www.seeopro.eu/ISBN-publication.pdf>.
- Lynch, Z., B. Basarabová, and B. Loudová Stralczynská. 2023. "(non)Sustainable Development of Early Childhood Education and Care in the Slovak Republic and the Czech Republic." *Eunomia—Rozwój Zrównowazony—Sustainable Development* 1 (104): 145–158.
- MEYS. 2023. Mimořádné Šetření k Počtům Ukrajinských Uprchlíků v Regionálním Školství/Special Study on the Number of Ukrainian Refugees in Regional Education. Ministry of Education, Youths and Sports Czech Republic. <https://www.msmt.cz/ministerstvo/novinar/pocty-ukrajinskych-deti-ve-skolach-se-oproti-zari-temer>.
- MI CR. 2023. "Number of Persons Granted a Residence Permit in Connection with the War in Ukraine." Ministry of Interior Czech Republic. <https://www.mvcr.cz/clanek/informativni-pocty-obyvatele-v-obcich.aspx>.
- Nygård, O. 2022. "Pre-Migration Status, Social Capital, and the Educational Aspirations of Children of Immigrants in Disadvantaged Swedish Schools." *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research* 66 (4): 580–593. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2021.1897878>.
- Oberhuemer, P., and I. Schreyer, Eds. 2024. *Early Childhood Workforce Profiles Across Europe: 33 Country Reports with Key Contextual Data*. Munich: State Institute for Early Childhood Research and Media Literacy. <http://www.seeopro.eu/Complete-Publication2024.pdf>.
- Obrovská, J., and K. S. Janků. 2021. "Resilience Capacity and Supportive Factors of Compulsory Education in Ethnic Minority Families: Mixed Methods Study of Czech Roma Mothers." *Contemporary Social Science* 16 (4): 448–463. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21582041.2020.1869813>.
- Oddy, J., M. Harewood, E. Masserano, and A. Lounasmaa. 2022. "Experiences of Forced Migration: Learning for Educators and Learners: A Report." *International Review of Psychiatry* 34 (6): 649–656. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540261.2022.2096403>.

- OECD. 2019. *Providing Quality Early Childhood Education and Care: Results from the Starting Strong Survey 2018*. TALIS. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/301005d1-en>.
- OECD. 2020. *OECD Economic Surveys: Czech Republic 2020*. OECD Economic Surveys: Czech Republic. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1b180a5a-en>.
- OECD. 2023. *Education at a Glance 2023: OECD Indicators*. Education at a Glance. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e13bef63-en>.
- Omeni, E. 2016. "Troubling Encounters: Exclusion, Racism and Responses of Male African Students in Poland". Edited by Jamie Halsall. *Cogent Social Sciences* 2 (1): 1212637. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2016.1212637>.
- Oprailová, E. 2016. *Předškolní Pedagogika*. Vydání 1 ed. Praha: Grada.
- PAQ. 2023. Ukrainian Refugee Integration: One Year On. PAQ Research. <https://www.paqresearch.cz/post/integrace-ukrajinskych-uprchliku-rok-pote>.
- PAQ Research. 2023. Integration of Refugees in the Labour Market and Housing. PAQ Research, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences. <https://www.paqresearch.cz/post/prijmy-a-chudoba-uprchliku-podzim2023>.
- Putcha, V., M. Neuman, O. Zaplotynska, and N. Sofiy. 2018. *Supporting the Early Childhood Workforce at Scale: Preschool Education in Ukraine*. Washington, D.C: Results for Development.
- Šafářová, K., M. Kavanová, M. Ostrý, A. Kořínek, M. Škvrňák, and M. Kunc. 2023. Vzdělávání Děti Uprchlíků v Česku/Education of Refugee Children in the Czech Republic. 6. Vlna Výzkumu Hlas Ukrajinců: Červen 2023. PAQ Research. <https://www.paqresearch.cz/post/vzdelavani-uprchlici-let-2023/>.
- Šedová, K., and R. Švaříček. 2013. "Jak Psát Kvalitativně Orientované Výzkumné Studie. Kvalita v Kvalitativním Výzkumu." *Pedagogická Orientace* 23 (4): 478–510. <https://doi.org/10.5817/PedOr2013-4-478>.
- Şengönül, T. 2022. "A Review of the Relationship Between Parental Involvement and Children's Academic Achievement and the Role of Family Socioeconomic Status in This Relationship." *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction* 12. 2. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.12.02.04>.
- Stanković, D., K. Zorić, and O. Jovanović, eds. 2020. *Inclusive Education for Every Child in a Multicultural Society: INEDU Handbook 2*. Centre for Interactive Pedagogy. https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/project-result-content/be9338ce-4034-486e-82a5-42ed08ae0129/INEDU_Handbook2_full.pdf.
- Stevens, K. E., I. Siraj, and K. Kong. 2023. "A Critical Review of the Research Evidence on Early Childhood Education and Care in Refugee Contexts in Low- and Middle-Income Countries." *International Journal of Child Care and Education Policy* 17 (1): 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40723-023-00109-4>.
- Tobin, J., and F. Kurban. 2018. "Preschool Practitioners' and Immigrant Parents' Beliefs About Academics and Play in the Early Childhood Educational Curriculum in Five Countries." *Orbis Scholae* 4 (2): 75–87. <https://doi.org/10.14712/23363177.2018.127>.
- UN. 2015. *Transforming Our World. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. New York: United Nations.
- Van Ee, E., M. Sleijpen, R. J. Kleber, and M. J. Jongmans. 2013. "Father-Involvement in a Refugee Sample: Relations Between Posttraumatic Stress and Caregiving." *Family Process* 52 (4): 723–735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/famp.12045>.
- Vigil, D., and S. Lynn Lopez. 2020. "Countering Educational Inequities in Refugee and Immigrant Communities: Family Navigational Strategies in Educational Settings." *New Directions for Higher Education* 191:43–54. <https://doi.org/10.1002/he.20381>.
- Vindrola, S., G. Ghawi, I. Borisova, and V. Chopra. 2023. "Building Bright Futures: How to Integrate Ukraine's Refugee Children Through Early Childhood Education and Care". ED627656. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED627656>.
- Weikart, D. P. 2000. *Early Childhood Education: Need and Opportunity. Fundamentals of Educational Planning* 65. Paris: UNESCO: International Institute for Educational Planning.
- Yosso, T. J. 2005. "Whose Culture Has Capital? A Critical Race Theory Discussion of Community Cultural Wealth." *Race Ethnicity and Education* 8 (1): 69–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1361332052000341006>.